

INFLUENCE OF THE NANOCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE ON THE PAPER BARRIER PROPERTIES

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Abstract: *Nowadays research is focused on searching materials from natural resources to decrease the amount of plastic waste. Using bio-based materials is one of the options for replacing the currently used polyethylene film plastic packaging. Paper is a natural material thus appropriate for replacing plastic packaging. In Europe, more than 40% of paper and board are already used for packaging. Currently, research in paper industry is focused to improve surface properties, especially barrier properties, such as oil and grease resistance, water vapour permeability and oil migration. Regular coated papers do not provide sufficient barrier properties. Nanocrystalline cellulose (CNC) is a natural material used in different fields and could also be used as an additive in coatings in paper industry.*

The main research was focused on the replacement of synthetic polymer with bio-based material. Here, we present an option of using the CNC in paper coatings to improve barrier properties, such as oil absorption (Cobb Unger), grease resistance (KIT test), water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) at different test conditions as well as heptane vapour transmission rate (HVTR). Coatings of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) with different addition of CNC (0%, 1%, 3% and 5%) were prepared. These coatings were characterized and applied on two different basic papers. The barrier properties were measured and results show, that CNC in PVA coatings applied on the paper surface improved barrier properties. Therefore, the utilization of CNC would expand the usability of such paper in different applications where high barrier properties are needed.

Keywords: nanocrystalline cellulose, paper, coating, barrier properties

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays research is focused on preserving the environment and to decrease the amount of plastic waste. The large part of waste presents the packaging from various polyolefin-based polymers used in transport or packaging for different foods. The trend is to reduce waste, and to use more environmentally friendly materials instead of synthetic polymers. One of the options is to use natural materials, such as paper or paperboard, made of cellulose fibers and its surface treated with various synthetic or natural polymers.

Paper is an excellent material for different uses, such as packaging, printing, writing, etc., because of its good mechanical properties, small masses, biodegradability, and recyclability. In Europe, more than 40% of paper and paperboard are used for packaging. 50% of packaging is used for various food products; (i) dry products (tea, coffee, sugar, flour, cereals, baked products, etc.), (ii) frozen or heated food, ice-cream, (iii) drinks (milk, milk products, and juices), (iv) sugar products and chocolate, (v) fast food and (vi) fresh products (fruits, vegetables, meat, and fish). For all these products we can use a paper bag, wrapping paper, multilayer paper bag, or cardboard (Kapun et al., 2019).

Currently, research in the paper industry is dedicated to improve surface properties, especially barrier properties, such as grease resistance (KIT test), absorption oil (Cobb Unger), and water vapour permeability (WVTR). Regular coated papers do not provide sufficient barrier properties and for that reason, the research is a focused on finding materials for coatings with improved barrier properties and to replace polyethylene film. One of the options is the addition of the nanocellulose obtained from natural cellulose. By definition, nanocellulose has at least one dimension less than 100 nanometers in size, either diameter or length. Nanocellulose has good mechanical properties, low density, it is biodegradable and biocompatible biomaterial (Kargarzadeh et al., 2018). Due to its excellent properties, research on different areas of application has increased exponentially since 2000. It is used in composite material, nonwovens, cosmetics, food products, and in the paper industry where it can be used as filler or as an additive in coatings. Basically, there are three types of nanocellulose; nanofibrillated cellulose (NFC), bacterial nanocellulose (BNC), and nanocrystalline cellulose (CNC). The size and shape of the CNC are depended on the extraction process obtained from cellulose. The usually rod-shaped CNC has a diameter of 3-10 nm and length between 100 nm and 500 nm (Kargarzadeh et al., 2018). Company Navitas is the only producer of CNC in Slovenia. Its CNC is in a water suspension form, conc. 6-10 % (wt), and the particles have 10-15 nm in diameter and with length of 150-300 nm (Navitas).

CNC has a great potential in paper coatings as an additive or as a substitute for a synthetic binder (Hubbe et al. 2017, Lang et al. 2016, Juhant Grkman et al. 2016), due to its specific properties, such as high specific surface and good mechanical properties. The main benefit of the addition of CNC to paper coatings is the improved barrier properties.

Hubbe *et al.* (Hubbe et al., 2017) have used different types of nanocellulose in paper coatings utilizing different coating techniques. Results of their research are presented in table 1. Lang *et al.* added different amounts of CNC (up to 0.4%) in alkyl ketene dimer (AKD) emulsion and applied such emulsion on the paper surface. This way they improved mechanical properties, barrier properties (Lang et al.) and decreased oxygen permeability. Juhant Grkman *et al.* decreased the oil absorption on the coated paper by 50 % with the addition of 1 % of CNC into the pigment paper coating (Juhant Grkman et al., 2016).

Table 1: Nanocrystalline cellulose in different matrix polymer (Hubbe et al.)

Type of nanocellulose	Matrix polymer	Key findings	Literature citation
CNC	Chitosan	Higher mechanical properties and WVTR were achieved	Dehnad et al. 2014b
CNC	Chitosan	WVTR was decreased by the CNC, and there was less swelling	Khan et al. 2012
CNC	PVA	Mechanical and thermal performance of the films was increased by including the CNC	George et al. 2010
CNC	PVA	Tensile and thermal properties of the PVA films were enhanced	Lee et al. 2009
CNC	PVA, chitosan	Antimicrobial, oxygen barrier, and mechanical property improvements were demonstrated	Li et al. 2015b
CNC	PVA	Increasing CNC tended to increase the water vapor barrier, while maintaining transparency	Pereira et al. 2014
CNC	PLA	Adding 3% CNC decreased water and oxygen permeability, which was the optimum	Sanchez-G. & Lagaron 2010
CNC	Starch	Mechanical properties and resistance to air were improved by the CNC addition	Yang et al. 2014

The main research was focused on the replacement of synthetic polymer with bio-based material. One of the options was using CNC in paper coatings to improve barrier properties, such as oil absorption (Cobb Unger), grease resistance (KIT test), WVTR at different test conditions as well as heptane vapour transmission rate (HVTR). Coatings of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) with different addition of CNC were prepared. They were characterized and applied

on two different basic papers with laboratory coater Sumet. The barrier properties were measured on coated papers.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Coatings preparation and rheological properties of coatings

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), Mowiol 4-98 in dry form was used to prepare 25% of PVA suspension. In PVA suspension we added different amounts of CNC (0%, 1%, 3%, 5%). CNC was added as a homogenous water suspension with conc. 3.92 % (wt.), pH of CNC suspension was 8.05 and viscosity was 1460 mPas, measured on Brookfield viscometer (R4, 100 rpm, T=9 °C). Rheological properties of coatings are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Rheological properties of coatings

	<i>PVA</i>	<i>PVA + 1 % CNC</i>	<i>PVA + 3 % CNC</i>	<i>PVA + 5 % CNC</i>
Viscosity. (mPas)	242	296	510	890
pH value	6.88	7.06	7.10	7.28
Concentration (%)	25.05	24.58	24.66	24.62

As expected, the viscosity and pH values of coatings increased as shown in Table 2.

2.2 Application of coatings on a paper surface

Coatings were applied on two different papers; (i) paper A, grammage 44 g/m², (ii) paper B, grammage 68 g/m² with laboratory coater Sumet using film press technique. Process parameters were optimized, regarding the rheological properties of the coatings. 6 g/m² of coating was applied on paper A and paper B.

Barrier properties were measured on coated papers, such as water vapour transmission (WVTR) by standard SIST ISO 2528:2018, and ASTM D 1653-93:1999, oil absorption (Cobb Unger) by standard SCAN-P 37:77, heptane vapour transmission (HVTR) by ICP method and grease resistance (KIT test) by standard T 559 cm-02.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Coated papers A

Coated papers A gave the highest grease resistance (KIT value 12) by adding 1%, 3%, and 5% CNC in coatings (Figure 1). Oil absorption decreased with the addition of CNC (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Grease resistance of tested paper A and coated papers A

Figure 2: Oil absorption of tested paper A and coated papers A

VTR was measured at different test conditions; (i) 85 ± 2 % RH, 23 ± 1 °C, (ii) 50 ± 5 % RH, 23 ± 2 °C. Results are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4. WVTR decreased with the addition of 1% CNC in the coating, compared with uncoated paper A.

Heptane vapour transmission rate (HVTR) was similar to sample PVA+1% CNC, PVA+3% CNC, PVA+5% CNC, compared to sample with only PVA coating (Figure 5).

Figure 3: WVTR at 85 % RH, 23 °C of tested paper A and coated papers A

Figure 4: WVTR at 50 % RH, 23 °C of tested paper A and coated papers A

Figure 5: HVTR of tested paper A and coated papers A

3. 2 coated papers B

The highest grease resistance was obtained (KIT value 12) with all coatings on paper B (Figure 6).

Oil absorption decreased in a similar manner (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Grease resistance of tested paper B and coated papers B

Figure 7: Oil absorption of tested paper B and coated papers B

The addition of CNC into the coating did not significantly decrease the WVTR, compared to the sample with PVA coating (Figure 8 and 9). The same results were observed for the heptane transmission rate. (Figure 10).

Figure 8: WVTR at 85 % RH, 23 °C of tested paper B and coated papers B

Figure 9: WVTR at 50 % RH, 23 °C of tested paper B and coated papers B

Figure 10: HVTR of tested paper B and coated papers B

4 CONCLUSION

Research results showed, that using CNC in paper coatings gives an option to replace part of synthetic polymer. Coatings with added CNC have different rheological properties.

Barrier properties on both coated papers are different. Coated papers B with added CNC had lower Cobb Unger level comparable with coated papers A. The grease resistance is comparable on both coated papers, both have the highest KIT 12. The water vapour transmission rate on both coated papers with added 1% of CNC had the lowest value. Therefore, the utilization of CNC would expand the usability of such paper in different applications where high barrier properties are needed.

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